

QUASI-STATIC AND FATIGUE EVALUATION OF LASER MACHINED CF-PPS AND CF-PEI COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the mechanical properties of laser cut thermoplastic CFRP compared to conventionally machined samples. Polyphenylene sulfide (CF-PPS) and polyetherimide (CF-PEI) matrix materials were used for the experiments. The laminate was a $[0_4,90_4]_T$ 5-harness satin weave layup. Different cutting strategies such as contour and multipass cutting were applied to assess the effect on the heat affected zone (HAZ). The mechanical properties were determined by conducting standard quasi-static and fatigue tests including a $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test to measure the in-plane shear strength. In addition, for each parameter set the extent of the different HAZ types were visually evaluated by photomicrographs in order to correlate the mechanical behavior with the observable damage. The work is part of a Eurostars project (CoCompact) with Element Materials Technology Hitchin Ltd, Laser on Demand GmbH and Laser Zentrum Hannover e.V.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, Carbon fire reinforced materials (CFRPs) have many potential applications within the sectors of transportations, energy and biomechanical engineering. In the aerospace and automotive industries, the reduction of weight is a requirement in order to enhance the dynamic performance and to contribute significantly to energy and CO₂ savings. Composite materials can be composed of thermoset or thermoplastic matrix. Thermoplastic materials compared to thermosets have several advantages; they can be welded, recycled and repaired. To achieve a widespread dissemination of CFRPs, manufacturing and processing costs need to be optimized. Therefore, fast and cost effective manufacturing processes are required for reinforced thermoplastic materials. Many opportunities can be found in laser based processing methods in these fields [1-3] offering large potential for further improvements although they still require more establishment within industry.

Mechanical cutting techniques such as milling require water to cool the parts and also to carry away the debris and reduce dust. The effect of the water on the parts often has to be mitigated by drying of the parts after cutting. This adds significant time to the manufacturing process. Another consequence is that these techniques are not force-free. In addition to the effects of the water and the force, wear occurs to the machining tools which means that they have to be changed frequently to maintain the tolerances on the components being cut and this adds to the cycle time. In recent years, many companies have focused their interest in water jet technologies. Although good quality can be achieved with this method, delamination in the material can be produced. Moreover, the waterjet technique requires a pilot drill, when a hole is made or the cutting does not start in the edge of the material. Both techniques, mechanical cutting and water jet, are not force-free and the water jet method occasionally requires help from the mechanical cutting methods.

Laser machining of CFRP provides a processing method that is force-free, wear-free, fast and automated for cutting and trimming. However, for cutting processes the heat generated can lead to heat affected zones (HAZ), which can be distinguished by areas with vaporization or decomposition of the matrix material, creating porosity, or delimitation within the laminates. The HAZ can have an influence on the mechanical properties of CFRP structures, as studied in [4,5] and the challenge is to reduce the HAZ to the minimum possible. The moisture content in the HAZ is also important to take into account, as it can affect the mechanical properties. These results were studied in [6], showing that increasing the moisture content of the processed material results in wider HAZs, and hence in decreased in plane shear properties.

This paper focuses on how the different techniques used in laser cutting can lead to reduced HAZ and therefore improved mechanical properties. Likewise, the use and significance of the different standards on the evaluation of the laser and conventional cut thermoplastic CFRP is studied.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

Two different Tencate Cetex[®] thermoplastic CFRP sheets were used for the experiments with two different thicknesses (1.24 mm and 2.48 mm). They were composed by Polyphenylene sulfide (CF-PPS) and polyetherimide (CF-PEI) as matrix materials. The material characteristics are shown in Table 1.

Material	Fabric	Thickness (mm)	Number of layers	Fibre orientation
CF-PPS	5-harness satin weave	1.24	4	[(0) ₂ , (90) ₂] _T
CF-PEI	5-harness satin weave	1.24	4	[(0) ₂ , (90) ₂] _T
CF-PPS	5-harness satin weave	2.48	8	[(0) ₄ , (90) ₄] _T
CF-PPS	5-harness satin weave	2.48	8	[(0) ₄ , (90) ₄] _T

Table 1: CFRP materials used for the experiments

In order to cut the coupons with laser technologies, a cutting method using a single mode fibre laser by Rofin-Sinar Laser GmbH was utilized. The maximum power of the laser is $P_L=1.5kW$ and the wavelength of the emission is $\lambda=1070nm$. The laser beam is guided through an optical fibre to a collimator and a scan head, which deflects the laser beam within a 2D working field. In order to focus, a f-theta objective was used. With the aim to maintain the CFRP laminates cold, a cross jet was used to generate constant nitrogen flow. A second cross jet was used to protect the optics against particles. The setup is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Laser cutting method setup [6]

Two different laser strategies were used to cut the samples: contour and multipass strategies. In the contour strategy only a single pass at low scanning speed v_s is carried out on the same contour, therefore the heat input is high. However, the multipass strategy uses various passes at high scanning speeds on the same contour, reducing the heat input due to short interaction times and hence, improving the quality of the cutting surface [3]. Both laser strategies are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Scheme of contour and multipass strategies

As the input energy to cut the material depends on the thickness of the materials [4], two set of tests were performed. In order to evaluate the properties of the matrix (in plane-shear strength) and the defects of the edges combined, a modified Open Hole Tension Test was carried out for the thinner materials (thickness =1.24 mm). It consists of $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test combined with Open Hole Tension (OHT) test to measure the in-plane shear strength and the edge defects. In addition, fatigue tests with this configuration (Open Hole Tension at $\pm 45^\circ$) were conducted.

The laser cutting method used in this case was contour. For the mechanical process method, a diamond coated saw was used and the holes were milled in the cutting strategy named as reference. The laser parameters used for 1.24 mm thickness are given in Table 2.

Material	Cutting strategy	Number of passes (n)	Laser power (P_L) [kW]	Scanning speed (v_s) [$m s^{-1}$]
CF-PPS	Contour	1	1.5	0.17
CF-PEI	Contour	1	1.5	0.14

Table 2: Laser parameters used for OHT test at $\pm 45^\circ$ coupons (1.24 mm thickness).

By analyzing the results obtained in this set of tests, another set of standard tests were performed, but this time with thicker materials (2.48 mm). The first test was performed according to ASTM D2344 (Standard test method for short-beam strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials). As the dimensions of the coupons are reduced (5 mm x 15 mm), it was very probable that the mechanical properties were affected by the heat affected zone (HAZ). The laser parameters used to cut the samples are given in Table 3. The first parameter used was contour, as explained above, only one pass was needed to cut the sample and the heat input was considerable.

In the multipass strategy, several actions can be performed between the passes in order to cool down the material, reduce the heat input and hence, to reduce the HAZ. These actions can be, for instance, break times to allow the material to cool down, or establish a variable increasing break time over the time of the process to keep a constant temperature level. For the variable break, the times were varied between $t=0.5 \dots 30s$. Figure 3 shows the maximum temperature achieved cutting the ASTM D2344 coupons using 5s break between passes and using a variable break.

Based on the actions described above, three multipass strategies were used. For CF-PPS material, the first multipass strategy (Tth9) used a speed of 1.3m/s, 24 passes and time break of 3s. For Tth1 and Tth2, in order to improve the quality of the cutting surface, the scanning speed was increased to 3 m/s and a variable break was established. The difference between Tth2 and Tth1 was that in Tth2 two

parallel lines separated by 35 μm were used, therefore the number of repetitions decreased as Table 3 shown.

Figure 3: Maximum temperature in CFPPS in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using constant and variable break times

Condition	Material	Cutting strategy	Number of passes (n)	Scanning speed (v_s) [m s^{-1}]	Laser power (P_L) [kW]	Action between passes
C	CF-PPS	Contour	1	0.07	1.5	-
Tth9	CF-PPS	Multipass	24	1.3	1.5	$t_{\text{break}}=3\text{s}$
Tth1	CF-PPS	Multipass	80	3	1.5	$t_{\text{break}}=0.5...30\text{s}$
Tth2	CF-PPS	Multipass (2 lines)	27 (x2)	3	1.5	$t_{\text{break}}=0.5...30\text{s}$

Table 3: Laser parameters used in CF/PPS coupons for short beam tests

In the case of the CF-PEI material, contour strategy was used as the first laser cutting method. The multipass strategies were different to the strategies used in CF-PPS material. The multipass Tth9 used a low scanning speed of 1.3 m/s, 24 passes and a time of break of 3s. For Tth6 condition, 4 passes with a break time between them of 3s were used. Each one of these 4 passes was composed of 12 passes using 5 % of the laser power ($P_L=5\%$) with no break time between passes. In addition, 13 more passes were used, utilizing the maximum laser power (1.5 kW) with 3 s of break. Finally, the Tth7 multipass strategy used 65 passes with a variable break, using the maximum power of the laser (1.5kW).

Condition	Material	Cutting strategy	Number of passes (n)	Scanning speed (v_s) [m s^{-1}]	Laser power (P_L) [kW]	Action between passes
C	CF-PEI	Contour	1	3	1.5	-
Tth9	CF-PEI	Multipass	24	1.3	1.5	$t_{\text{break}}=3\text{s}$
Tth6	CF-PEI	Multipass	65	3	5% of 1.5 +1.5	$t_{\text{break}}=0.5...30\text{s}$
Tth7	CF-PEI	Multipass	65	3	1.5	$t_{\text{break}}=0.5...30\text{s}$

Table 4: Laser parameters used in CF-PEI coupons for short beam tests

Another set of Open Hole Compression (OHC) tests was carried out according to ASTM D6484, as the tests under compression are sensitive to the defects on the edges.

In these tests a contour cutting strategy was not used due to the results obtained in the short-beam tests. The laser parameters used for OHC compression tests for CF-PPS coupons are provided in Table 5. For the condition Tth1, the scanning speed, as used for short beam tests, was 3 m/s. However, the number of passes was increased to 110. This is due to the size of the coupons; by increasing the size of

the sample the heat expansion effects become apparent and the number of passes or repetitions raises. Two more parameters were used, Tth8 and Tth9. For both parameters the scanning speed was 1.25 m/s and 24 repetitions. Nevertheless, for Tth8 condition, a time break of 3 s was used between passes and for Tth9, a variable break between repetitions was established.

Condition	Material	Cutting strategy	Number of passes (n)	Scanning speed (v_s) [$m s^{-1}$]	Laser power (P_L) [kW]	Action between passes
Tth1	CF-PPS	Multipass	110	3	1.5	-
Tth8	CF-PPS	Multipass	24	1.25	1.5	$t_{break}=0.5...30s$
Tth9	CF-PPS	Multipass	24	1.25	1.5	$t_{break}=3s$

Table 5: Laser parameters used in CF-PPS coupons for OHC Tests

Regarding the CF-PEI material, the parameters chosen are given in Table 6. For Tth8 and Tth9 in CF-PEI material, the actions taken between repetitions were the same as for CF-PPS material, however the speed increased to 1.3 m/s. The scanning speed for Tth6 was 3 m/s with a total of 65 passes.

Condition	Material	Cutting strategy	Number of passes (n)	Scanning speed (v_s) [$m s^{-1}$]	Laser power (P_L) [kW]	Action between passes
Tth6	CF-PEI	Multipass	65	3	1.5	$t_{break}=0.5...30s$
Tth8	CF-PEI	Multipass	24	1.3	1.5	$t_{break}=0.5...30s$
Tth9	CF-PEI	Multipass	24	1.3	1.5	$t_{break}=3s$

Table 6: Laser parameters used in CF-PEI coupons for OHC tests

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The maximum shear stress results of the Open Hole Tension (OHT) at $\pm 45^\circ$ are given in Figure 4. Both materials, CF-PPS and CF-PEI, were used in these tests, with 1.24 mm thickness. The maximum shear stress was calculated taking into account the diameter of the hole. The results obtained in the reference cutting for both materials are slightly higher than the contour laser method. However, the error bars overlap in all the cases and the results obtained were comparable. Although the HAZ zone in the contour strategy is noticeable, as shown in Figure 5, this is not reflected on the results.

Figure 4: Maximum shear stress in OHT tests at $\pm 45^\circ$

Figure 5: Holes cut with contour laser strategy (left) and milled holes, reference (right).

The S-N curve for CF-PPS material with 1.24mm thickness is shown in Figure 6. As it can be observed, the S-N curve of the fatigue tests is similar for both methods, the contour strategy and the reference. Once again, damage observable of the HAZ is not reflected in the fatigue results.

Figure 6: S-N curve of CF-PPS in OHT at $\pm 45^\circ$

Before the results of the short beam test are presented and discussed, the microscopic images of the different short-beam test coupons are provided. Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the microscopic images of CF-PPS and CF-PEI materials respectively. The reference coupons were cut with a diamond coated saw. The HAZ in the contour strategy is very wide, occupying the width of the sample in the case of the CF-PEI, see Figure 8. The HAZ in the contour strategy is larger for thicker coupons. This can be observed by comparing Figure 5 and Figure 7 a) for CF-PPS and Figure 8 for CF-PEI. In the multipass strategy, the HAZ decreases as the scanning speed increases, being considerably narrow for the conditions Tth1 and Tth2 for CF-PPS and Tth6 and Tth7 for CF-PEI materials.

Figure 7: Microscopic images of CF-PPS short-beam samples. a) Contour, b) M1 (Slow multipass), c) Tth1 (Fast multipass), d) Tth2 (Fast multipass) and e) Reference.

Figure 8: Microscopic images of CF-PEI short-beam samples. a) Contour, b) M1 (Slow multipass), c) Tth6 (Fast multipass), d) Tth7 (Fast multipass) and e) Reference.

The short-beam test results according to ASTM D2344 are shown in Figure 9 for CF-PPS and in Figure 10 for CF-PEI. Firstly, for CF-PPS material, a correlation between the width of the damage due to the heat (Figure 7) and the short-beam strength is clearly seen. As Figure 9 shows, the lowest strength in the short beam test corresponds to the contour strategy which gives the widest HAZ. The Tth1 and Tth2 strategies (fast multipass) showed higher values than the low scanning speed multipass strategy (Tth9), with larger HAZ. However, no noticeable difference between Tth1 and Tth2 (multipass with two lines) in the short beam strength was found. The short-beam strength for the reference for CF-PPS was slightly higher than the laser strategies.

Regarding CF-PEI, the contour strategy exhibited the lowest short-beam strength with a significant difference compared to the multipass strategies; this is due to the HAZ affecting the whole sample. The strength in the multipass strategy Tth9 was lower than Tth6 and Tth7 parameters, as the heat damage was larger. The reference, in this case, corresponded to lower values than the multipass strategies Tth7 and Tth8. Between the latter laser cutting methods, no significant difference in the results were noticed.

Figure 9: Short-beam strength (MPa) for CF-PPS

Figure 10: Short-beam strength (MPa) for CF-PEI

Open Hole Compression tests were also performed following ASTM D6484, and the results obtained for both materials, CF-PPS and CF-PEI are given in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 11: Max stress (MPa) for OHC tests in CF-PPS.

Figure 12: Max stress (MPa) for OHC tests in CF-PEI.

In the CF-PPS composite, the multipass strategy parameters with lower scanning speed (1.25 m/s), Tth8 and Tth9 did not present any significant difference between them. Tth8 used a time of break 3 s,

whilst in Tth9 a variable break maintaining a constant low temperature was established. However, by increasing the scanning speed to 3m/s the maximum stress raised, as the results shown in Figure 11. Hence, there is a clear trend in the results between the mechanical properties and the scanning speed. The reference cut, in this case, showed better results.

For CF-PEI material, the same trend is followed as in CF-PPS. The slow multipass strategies, with 1.3m/s of scanning speed, showed the lowest strength. Therefore, no difference in the strength between Tt8 (constant break $t_{break}=3s$) and Th9 (variable break $t_{break}=0.5...30s$) was found. The parameter Tth6 with higher scanning speed was hardly higher. It can be seen in Figure 12 that the reference cutting method presented upper strength.

9 CONCLUSIONS

This paper evaluates the influence of the laser processing method and hence the HAZ on the mechanical properties of the CF-PPS and CFPEI composite materials. Moreover, the results were compared with a traditional mechanical cutting method (diamond coated saw cut). First of all, thinner materials (1.24 mm thickness) were evaluated using Open Hole Tension tests at $\pm 45^\circ$, in order to evaluate the properties of the matrix and the defects on the edges. The laser cutting strategy used was contour, with the highest heat input, and the results obtained for static and fatigue tests were comparable.

Secondly, thicker materials (2.48 mm thickness) were used due to the results obtained in thinner materials. Short beam tests according to ASTM D2344 were performed. The results for both materials used showed that there is a correlation between the HAZ and the short-beam strength. Coupons with the largest HAZ (contour) gave the lowest shear beam strength results. The results obtained for multipass strategies were comparable to the reference cutting method.

In the Open Hole Compression tests following ASTM D6484, the reference cutting method showed higher strength results than the laser cutting strategies. However, within the cutting laser methods a trend was observed with increasing the scanning speed. The higher the scanning speed, the better the mechanical properties obtained.

By comparing the overall results, it can be concluded that the HAZ affects the mechanical results. However, the HAZ can be reduced using multipass strategies leading to improved mechanical properties. Within the multipass strategies, the scanning speed was the parameter that has major influence in the quality of the cut. The thickness of the materials also has a big influence on the HAZ as the energy needed for a full cut is significantly rising for thicker materials.

The laser machining for CFRP provides a fast and automated cutting, being a force-free strategy. Moreover, by optimizing the parameters used in the laser cutting strategy, the mechanical properties can achieve values comparable to the traditional methods of cutting.

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